

Fostering the clean transport transition for a healthy place to live!

Co-generation of hydrogen and electricity with high-temperature fuel cells

D7.1: Website and communication material

WP 7 , T 7.3

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services).

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services).

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).

Versions

Revision Version	Date	Changes	Changes made by Partner
0.0	10.04.2017	First release – document skeleton and project identity	Mattia Malfatti (FBK)
0.1	18.04.2017	Added info on project identity, website and first communication package.	Mattia Malfatti (FBK)
1.0	02.05.2017	Final revision	Mattia Malfatti (FBK) Luigi Crema (FBK)

Table of Content

0	Introduction	5
1	Project Identity	6
1.1.1	CH2P logo design.....	6
1.1.2	CH2P claim.....	8
1.1.3	Identity package	8
1.1.4	Templates.....	8
2	Project website	10
3	Communication material	12
3.1.1	Project publicity (stickers, posters,etc.)	12
3.1.2	Postcard.....	12
3.1.3	Brochures	12

List of Figures

Figure 1.	CH2P Logo (different version)	6
Figure 2.	Concept of CH2P logo.....	6
Figure 3.	CH2P logo composition.	7
Figure 4.	CH2P Logo manual.	7
Figure 5.	CH2P business card, folder, headed paper and block notes.....	8
Figure 6.	CH2P documents template.	9
Figure 7.	CH2P presentation template.....	9
Figure 8.	CH2P website.	10
Figure 9.	CH2P stickers.....	12
Figure 10.	CH2P postcard.....	12

0 Introduction

To achieve European ambitions to reduce global emissions of greenhouse gases by 80% before 2050, emissions of the transport sector and of the energy sectors will need to decrease drastically.

Today, the Hydrogen Economy offers ready solutions to decarbonize the transport sector. Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) close to be deployed in the market in increasing numbers: because of this a network of hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) first has to exist.

In the medium-long term, Green Hydrogen (production of hydrogen by renewable energy sources) is figured as the target technology to decarbonize the different energy sectors, but these technologies needs to become commercially attractive in order to foster the development of clean transport sector.

What we can do in the meantime?

To accelerate this process, **CH2P aims at building a transition technology for early infrastructure deployment**, developing a new technology for the **future network of HRS**, using widely available carbon-lean natural gas (NG) or bio-methane to produce hydrogen and power through Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) technology.

CH2P aims at cogenerate hydrogen and electricity with high efficiency (up to 90%) and with reduced environmental impact compared to conventional technologies, pointing at a target cost for the hydrogen produced below 4,5 €/kg. The technology available at the end of the project should be scaled up for deployment at larger retail sites, moving the hydrogen production from the demo sites to the commercial refuelling stations in short time. This can pave the way to feed extensive fleets of Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEV's) – such as cars, buses and trains – accelerating the transition to clean technologies based on hydrogen.

1 Project Identity

1.1.1 CH2P logo design

Figure 1. CH2P Logo (all version)

Figure 1 shows the final different version of the CH2P logo. The final logo of the project is the result of a creative process, coordinated by FBK in collaboration with an external communication agency in charge of the logo design, in order to better communicate the objectives of the project. This final version is the results of a participate selection process among all the CH2P partners on a basis of three different solutions. The winner is the solution which better communicate the concept of energy reaction and transformation, in line with the the primary objective to realize a cogeneration of hydrogen, heat and power using Solid Oxide Cell technology fuelled by methane-rich gases, with a reduction of carbon footprint by an extremely high overall system efficiency.

ENERGY AND CREATION

Energy is always the product of a **transformation**.

What makes the difference is the cost, in terms of the environment and efficiency, of this transformation.

A metaphor that describes a clean energy multiplication process is undoubtedly that of **cell mitosis**: What can we imagine more natural and green?

Figure 2. Concept of CH2P logo

As shown in Figure 2, this clean transformation process could be inspired by the process of cell mitosis. By this way, starting from a single molecule of methane (stylized with a single cyan circle), the **transformation process** moves to a double molecule that ideally represent an H2

molecule to finally move forward to something new represented by the green circle that will push to the necessary **transition of green energy production**. Figure 3 shows the logo composition in details.

Figure 3. CH2P logo composition.

A specific manual for the use of the CH2P logo has been done in order to define the main rules to guarantee an effective graphical representation of the logo in all the different applications (communication materials, stickers, posters, digital material, banner, etc.). It is important to notice that a proper palette is defined, together with the minimal dimension allowed for the usage of the logo and example of version in black/white and positive/negative format.

Figure 4. CH2P Logo manual.

1.1.2 CH2P claim

Fostering the clean transport transition for a healthy place to live!

The CH2P project is expected to impact on several key EU and FCH JU objectives, especially on to lower carbon emissions for hydrogen as well as power generation and to lower the cost of hydrogen for mobility creating synergies between the Energy and the Transport sectors.

In line with this objectives, CH2P claim outline which is the final goal of the project in supporting the transition to a clean mobility and allows the EU citizens to live, as soon as possible, in a more healthy place!

1.1.3 Identity package

The identity package of the CH2P project is composed by: business card, folders, headed paper and block notes. The communication material is already available in the printable version to be used – based on the request and necessity - in all the future planned communication and dissemination activities.

Figure 5. CH2P business card, folder, headed paper and block notes.

1.1.4 Templates

Dedicated templates for the internal reports and deliverables has been prepared and shared with the partners to uniform the overall project documentation.

Figure 6. CH2P documents template.

Based on the same principle, a dedicated presentation template in Power Point has been provided and shared to be used during the dissemination activities (conferences, fairs, etc.) and face to face internal or external meetings.

Figure 7. CH2P presentation template.

2 Project website

WEBSITE UNDER CONSTRUCTION
Check back soon!

This project has received funding from the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 735692. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, from Hydrogen Europe and N.ERGHY.

ABOUT

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To accelerate this process, CH2P aims at building a **transition technology** for early infrastructure deployment, developing a new technology for the future network of HRS, using widely available carbon-lean natural gas (NG) or bio-methane to produce hydrogen and power through **Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC)** technology. CH2P aims at cogenerate hydrogen and electricity with **high efficiency (up to 90%) and with reduced environmental impact compared to conventional technologies**, pointing at a target cost for the hydrogen produced below 4.5 €/kg. The technology available at the end of the project should be scaled up for deployment at larger retail sites, moving the hydrogen production from the demo sites to the commercial refueling stations in short time. This can pave the way to feed extensive fleets of Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) – such as cars, buses and trains – accelerating the transition to clean technologies based on hydrogen.

More info available on CH2P project webpage.

POWERED BY WORDPRESS.COM.

Figure 8. CH2P website.

The website design of the CH2P project was completed at the end of March (M2) in collaboration with an external communication agency in order to define the best structure and

the contents that could address the huge audience as possible, from the single EU citizen to the research institute to the governmental organization.

A dedicated domain and hosting have been purchased, setting up a first landing page with the link to the main information about the project before the end of the first project month (M1) on the 17th of February 2017, at the same time of the first press releases launched at international level regarding the kick-off of the project.

The dedicated address is short and clear, composed only by the project acronyms and the domain extension .eu to underline the belonging to the EU community:

<http://www.ch2p.eu/>

The website is currently under finalization and will be online in the first final version during the second half of May 2017 (M4) in comparison with the planned deadline (M3). These acceptable delay did not penalize the communication and dissemination activity of the project, that it is under construction in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.2) under preparation.

During the whole project, constant update of the website design and content will be done to align the website content to the activities carried on by the consortium.

3 Communication material

Different communication materials have been designed and prepared to be available for professional printing when necessary in events, conferences, publicity actions, etc.

3.1.1 Project publicity (stickers, posters, etc.)

Figure 9. CH2P stickers.

3.1.2 Postcard

A first elementary version of the CH2P postcard have been designed with the objective to increase visibility and attract the attention on CH2P project. The postcard is already available in a professional printing layout, to easily provide the consortium with a first communication material to spread at conferences, fairs and events.

A new version to address the non-technical audience and more suitable for general communication in order to increase awareness of EU citizen is already under design.

Figure 10. CH2P postcard.

3.1.3 Brochures

The first version of the project brochure is planned to be available by the end of year two in order to include some preliminar results and parameter tha coming out from the work carried on in the WP1 – CH2P technology scenario and design.